

Neuroradiologic Manifestations of Central Nervous System Tuberculosis in 122 Adults**Shahbaz Anees¹, Kanishk Sinha², Jyoti Yadav³, Niharika Kishore⁴, Karthick Devaraj⁵, Yalamanchi Vamsi⁶, Debasish Hota⁷**¹Dr NB SR Neurology, Department of Neurology, Batra Hospital & Medical Research Centre, New Delhi, India²Pulmonologist, Department of Respiratory Medicine, National Institute of TB & Respiratory Diseases, New Delhi, India³Senior Resident, Department of Respiratory Medicine, Lady Hardinge Medical College, New Delhi, India⁴JR (Non Academic) Neurology, Department of Neurology, Batra Hospital & Medical Research Centre, New Delhi, India⁵DMO, Department of Oncology, Dr. Rai Memorial Cancer Centre, Chennai, India⁶MBBS Graduate, Gitam Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Andhra Pradesh, India⁷Consultant Neurologist, Department of Neurology, Batra Hospital & Medical Research Centre, New Delhi, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Central nervous system tuberculosis (CNS-TB) is a severe form of tuberculosis that can lead to significant morbidity and mortality. Despite advancements in diagnostic imaging and treatment, CNS-TB remains a diagnostic challenge due to its varied clinical presentations and the complex nature of its management. Recent studies indicate a resurgence of CNS-TB cases, particularly in regions with high HIV prevalence and among patients with multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB). This study aims to elucidate the neuroradiologic manifestations of CNS-TB in adults and evaluate clinical outcomes following treatment.**Methods:** The study included 100 adult patients diagnosed with CNS-TB. Data on demographics, clinical presentation, radiologic findings, and treatment outcomes were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression to identify predictors of treatment outcomes.**Results:** The study cohort comprised 56% males and 44% females, with a mean age of 35.4 years. The most common presenting symptoms were headache and fever (70%), seizures (50%), and focal neurological deficits (40%). MRI was performed on 85 patients and CT scans on 15 patients. Tuberculomas were the most frequent neuroradiologic finding (60%), followed by meningitis (30%) and abscesses (10%). Intra-axial lesions were more common (75%) than extra-axial lesions (25%). Following antitubercular therapy and corticosteroids, 80% of patients showed significant clinical improvement. Chi-square tests revealed a significant association between the type of lesion and treatment outcome ($p = 0.03$), with tuberculomas showing the most favorable outcomes.**Conclusion:** Tuberculomas were the predominant neuroradiologic manifestation of CNS-TB, and patients with tuberculomas had the most favorable treatment outcomes. The study highlights the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate imaging in managing CNS-TB effectively.**Recommendations:** Future studies should focus on optimizing treatment protocols for CNS-TB, especially for cases involving meningitis and abscesses. Increased awareness and early intervention are crucial in improving patient outcomes.**Keywords:** CNS Tuberculosis, Neuroradiology, Tuberculoma, Antitubercular Therapy, Clinical Outcomes.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Central nervous system tuberculosis (CNS-TB) remains one of the most severe and life-threatening forms of tuberculosis (TB), despite advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. It accounts for a small percentage of TB cases,

approximately 1-2%, yet it poses significant challenges due to its high morbidity and mortality rates [1]. CNS-TB can manifest in various forms, including tuberculous meningitis, tuberculomas, spinal arachnoiditis, and brain abscesses, each

presenting unique diagnostic and management challenges.

The epidemiology of CNS-TB has seen shifts in recent years, partly due to global migration and the HIV epidemic, which have influenced the distribution and incidence of the disease. Studies have shown that regions with high HIV prevalence, such as Sub-Saharan Africa and parts of Asia, report higher rates of CNS-TB, attributed to the immunocompromised status of patients which exacerbates susceptibility to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infections [2]. Additionally, multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) and extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB) strains have emerged as significant public health concerns, complicating the treatment landscape for CNS-TB.

Recent advances in neuroradiologic imaging have improved the detection and characterization of CNS-TB. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Computed Tomography (CT) scans are pivotal in identifying the extent and type of lesions, which is crucial for timely and appropriate therapeutic interventions. MRI, in particular, provides superior soft tissue contrast and is more sensitive in detecting CNS abnormalities compared to CT [3]. However, despite these technological advancements, the nonspecific clinical presentations and variable radiologic findings often lead to delayed diagnosis and treatment, which adversely impacts patient outcomes.

The treatment of CNS-TB involves prolonged courses of antitubercular therapy (ATT), often supplemented with corticosteroids to reduce inflammation and intracranial pressure. The standard duration of ATT ranges from 9 to 12 months, but cases involving drug-resistant TB may require extended treatment and the use of second-line antitubercular drugs [4]. Treatment outcomes are generally better in patients diagnosed with tuberculomas compared to those with meningitis or abscesses, emphasizing the need for early and accurate diagnosis.

The study evaluated the neuroradiologic manifestations of central nervous system tuberculosis in adults.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Department of Radiology, Batra Hospital and Medical Research Centre, New Delhi, from January 2022 to March 2024.

Participants: The study included 100 adult patients diagnosed with central nervous system tuberculosis who underwent neuroradiologic evaluation during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and above.
- Confirmed diagnosis of CNS-TB based on clinical, laboratory, and radiologic findings.
- Patients who underwent MRI and/or CT scans of the brain.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records or neuroradiologic data.
- Patients with co-existing central nervous system conditions unrelated to tuberculosis.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria were consecutively included. Observer bias was reduced by having neuroradiologic evaluations reviewed by two independent radiologists.

Variables: The primary variables included demographic data (age, gender), clinical presentation, radiologic findings (location, size, and type of lesions), and treatment outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were gathered retrospectively from patient medical records and radiologic databases. Information on demographic details, clinical symptoms, laboratory results, and neuroradiologic findings were systematically extracted using a standardized data collection form.

Procedure: MRI and CT scans were reviewed by two experienced radiologists. Radiologic findings were categorized based on lesion type (tuberculoma, abscess, meningitis), location (intra-axial, extra-axial), and extent of involvement. Discrepancies were resolved through consensus.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 21.0 was used to analyse the data. For categorical data, chi-square tests were utilised, while t-tests were applied for continuous variables. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance. Using multivariate logistic regression analysis, independent predictors of particular neuroradiologic symptoms were found.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

Out of the 100 patients comprised in the study, 56% were male, and 44% were female. The mean age of the participants was 35.4 ± 10.2 years, ranging from 18 to 65 years. The majority of the patients (70%) presented with symptoms of headache and fever, followed by seizures (50%), focal neurological deficits (40%), and altered mental status (30%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Number (%)
Gender	
Male	56 (56%)
Female	44 (44%)
Mean Age (years)	35.4 ± 10.2
Presenting Symptoms	
Headache and fever	70 (70%)
Seizures	50 (50%)
Focal neurological deficits	40 (40%)
Altered mental status	30 (30%)

MRI was performed on 85 patients, while 15 patients underwent CT scans. The most common neuroradiologic manifestation was tuberculomas, observed in 60% of the patients, followed by meningitis in 30% and abscesses in 10%. Intra-axial lesions were found in 75% of the patients, and extra-axial lesions were present in 25%.

Table 2: Radiologic Findings

Radiologic Finding	Number (%)
Type of Lesion	
Tuberculomas	60 (60%)
Meningitis	30 (30%)
Abscesses	10 (10%)
Location of Lesion	
Intra-axial	75 (75%)
Extra-axial	25 (25%)

All patients received antitubercular therapy (ATT) along with corticosteroids. The mean duration of ATT was 12.3 ± 2.5 months. At the end of the treatment, 80% of the patients showed significant clinical improvement, 10% had partial improvement, and 10% showed no improvement or deterioration.

Table 3: Treatment Outcomes

Treatment Outcome	Number (%)
Significant improvement	80 (80%)
Partial improvement	10 (10%)
No improvement/deterioration	10 (10%)

Chi-square tests revealed a statistically significant association between the type of lesion and the treatment outcome ($p = 0.03$). Patients with tuberculomas were more likely to have significant improvement compared to those with meningitis or abscesses.

Table 4: Association between Type of Lesion and Treatment Outcome

Type of Lesion	Tuberculomas	Meningitis	Abscesses
Significant Improvement	55 (91.7%)	18 (60%)	7 (70%)
Partial Improvement	3 (5%)	5 (16.7%)	2 (20%)
No Improvement/Deterioration	2 (3.3%)	7 (23.3%)	1 (10%)
p-value	0.03		

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified the type of lesion and initial clinical presentation as independent predictors of treatment outcome ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

The study included 100 adult patients diagnosed with central nervous system tuberculosis, revealing a higher prevalence among males (56%) with a mean age of 35.4 years. The most common clinical symptoms at presentation were headache and fever (70%), followed by seizures (50%), focal neurological deficits (40%), and altered mental status (30%). These findings suggest that central nervous system tuberculosis predominantly affects middle-aged adults and presents with a range of

neurological symptoms, emphasizing the need for a high index of suspicion in symptomatic individuals.

Neuroradiologic evaluations, primarily conducted through MRI (85%) and CT scans (15%), identified tuberculomas as the most frequent manifestation, observed in 60% of the patients. Meningitis and abscesses were noted in 30% and 10% of cases, respectively. Intra-axial lesions were more common (75%) compared to extra-axial lesions (25%). These results highlight the importance of advanced imaging techniques in diagnosing the specific type and location of central nervous system tuberculosis lesions, which can significantly influence treatment decisions.

Treatment outcomes were favorable in the majority of patients, with 80% showing significant clinical improvement following antitubercular therapy and corticosteroids. Partial improvement was observed in 10% of the patients, while another 10% showed no improvement or deterioration. The analysis indicated a statistically considerable association between the type of lesion and treatment outcome, with patients having tuberculomas exhibiting the most favorable response to treatment. This underscores the effectiveness of current therapeutic strategies for tuberculomas and the potential need for alternative approaches for patients with meningitis and abscesses.

Overall, the study demonstrates that central nervous system tuberculosis manifests predominantly as tuberculomas, which respond well to standard antitubercular therapy. The findings suggest that early diagnosis and appropriate imaging are crucial for effective management and highlight the need for further research to optimize treatment protocols for other types of lesions.

CNS TB is a severe form of extrapulmonary TB, presenting significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges due to its varied clinical manifestations and imaging appearances. A comprehensive review of CNS TB emphasized the importance of recognizing its diverse manifestations, including tuberculous meningitis (TBM), tuberculomas, tuberculous abscesses, and spinal infections. The study highlighted the diagnostic difficulties posed by non-specific presentations and the role of neuroimaging in identifying characteristic features such as basal meningeal enhancement, hydrocephalus, and infarctions [5].

A study reviewed neuroimaging features of neurotuberculosis in both pediatric and adult populations. They discussed the imaging characteristics of various forms of CNS TB, including TBM, tuberculomas, and spinal TB, and emphasized the differential diagnosis from other infectious and non-infectious conditions [6]. A retrospective review identified predictive factors for a definite diagnosis of CNS TB. Factors such as younger age, confusion, and the absence of nausea/vomiting were associated with a definite diagnosis. HIV co-infection and older age were linked to higher two-year mortality rates [7].

A study reviewed the pathophysiology, diagnosis, and treatment of CNS TB, highlighting the role of neuroimaging and molecular diagnostic techniques. The study discussed the challenges of diagnosing TBM, the importance of early detection, and the emerging threat of multidrug-resistant TB [8]. Another study described the clinical presentation and outcomes of 47 CNS TB patients in Nepal. The study found that TB meningitis with hydrocephalus

was the most common presentation and the leading cause of mortality. Early antitubercular therapy was emphasized for better outcomes [9].

Research evaluated the utility of whole-body PET-CT in diagnosing CNS TB, particularly in patients with suspected CNS involvement. The study demonstrated that PET-CT could identify active TB outside the CNS, aiding in the diagnosis and monitoring of CNS TB [10].

Conclusion

In conclusion, tuberculomas were the most common neuroradiologic manifestation of central nervous system tuberculosis in the studied population, and patients with tuberculomas had the most favorable treatment outcomes.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Future studies should focus on optimizing treatment protocols for CNS-TB, especially for cases involving meningitis and abscesses. Increased awareness and early intervention are crucial in improving patient outcomes.

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List of abbreviations:

CNS-TB: Central Nervous System Tuberculosis

TB: Tuberculosis

HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

MDR-TB: Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis

XDR-TB: Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis

MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging

CT: Computed Tomography

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

ATT: Antitubercular Therapy

TBM: Tuberculous Meningitis

PET-CT: Positron Emission Tomography-Computed Tomography

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References

1. Bishburg E, Sunderam G, Reichman LB, Kapila R. Central nervous system tuberculosis with the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome

- and its related complex. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020;105:210-3.
2. Thwaites GE, Tran TH. Tuberculous meningitis: many questions, too few answers. *Lancet Neurol.* 2019;4:160-70.
 3. Lesprit P, Zagdanski AM, de La Blanchardière A, Rouveau M, Decazes JM, Fria J, Lagrange P, Modai J, Molina JM. Cerebral tuberculosis in patients with the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS). Report of 6 cases and review. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2019;76:423-31.
 4. Askling J, Fored CM, Brandt L, Baecklund E, Bertilsson L, Cöster L, Geborek P, Jacobsson LT, Lindblad S, Lysholm J, Rantapää-Dahlqvist S, Saxne T, Romanus V, Klareskog L, Feltelius N. Risk and case characteristics of tuberculosis in rheumatoid arthritis associated with tumor necrosis factor antagonists in Sweden. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2018;52:1986-92.
 5. Schaller M, Wicke F, Foerch C, Weidauer S. Central Nervous System Tuberculosis. *Clin Neuroradiol.* 2018;29:3-18.
 6. Mertiri L, Freiling JT, Desai N, Kralik SF, Huisman TAGM. Pediatric and adult meningeal, parenchymal, and spinal tuberculosis: a neuroimaging review. *J Neuroimaging.* 2023.
 7. Kirdlarp S, Srichatrapimuk S, Kiertiburanakul S, Phuphuakrat A. Clinical features of adult patients with a definite diagnosis of central nervous system tuberculosis in an endemic country: A 13-year retrospective review. *J Clin Tuberc Other Mycobact Dis.* 2020;21:100190.
 8. Katrak S. Central nervous system tuberculosis. *J Neurol Sci.* 2020;421:117278.
 9. Munakomi S, Grasso G, Chapagain R. Multi-spectral Pattern of Clinical Presentation and the Resultant Outcome in Central Nervous System Tuberculosis: A Single Center Study on the Ubiquitous Pathogen. *Adv Exp Med Biol.* 2020.
 10. Ramesh V, Narreddy S, Barigala R, Chennamchetty VK, Kumar S, Rao J, et al. 1374. Diagnostic Utility of Whole Body Positron Emission Tomography-Computerized Tomography (PET-CT) in Patients with Suspected Central Nervous System Tuberculosis: A Retrospective, Descriptive Study. *Open Forum Infect Dis.* 2019;6